

Research Article

Effect of various plant growth regulators on in vitro plantlet regeneration from different explants of *Citrus sinensis* (L.)

Md. Tauhidul Islam†, Sumon Karmakar†, Mutasim Billah†, Nazmus Sakib, Md. Faruk Hasan, Md. Asadul Islam, Biswanath Sikdar and Uzzal Kumar Acharjee*

Professor Joarder DNA and Chromosome Research Laboratory, Department of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, University of Rajshahi, Rajshahi-6205, Bangladesh

†Equal contribution

*Corresponding author

ukarcc@gmail.com

Accepted: 20 April, 2020; Online: 02 May, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3780446>

Abstract: The present investigation was intended to establish an effective protocol for direct shoot regeneration as well as root induction of *Citrus sinensis* using seed germinated shoot tip and nodal segments. Surface sterilization of explants was attributed with NaOCl (Sodium hypochloride) in shoot tip and nodal segments for successful contamination free culture. For direct shoot proliferation, nodal segments and shoot tips showed effective results when it cultured aseptically on MS (Murashige and Skoog) medium containing different concentrations and combinations of BAP (Benzylamino purine), GA₃ (Gibberellic acids), NAA (Naphthalene acetic acid) and IAA (Indole acetic acid) the best result was observed in the combination of 1.5mg/l BAP+ 0.2 mg/l GA₃. The explants were inoculated on MS medium supplemented with 8g/l Agar and 30g/l sucrose, different combination and concentration of plant growth regulators was used for plantlet regeneration. Root induction has also done here using various concentration of IAA hormone. The highest number of root induction was found to be MS containing 2.0mg/l IAA. Induced roots were elongated properly at the same hormonal concentration after two weeks of inoculation. From the above findings, it is suggested that different hormonal concentration and combination has significant effect on the propagation of sweet orange plant. The established protocol would be helpful for direct plantlet regeneration as well as proliferation of this valuable fruit crop plants.

Keywords: *Citrus sinensis* (L.), shoot tip, nodal explants, growth regulators, micropropagation.

Introduction

Citrus sinensis (L.) is a most popular cultivated fruit plants belonging to the family of Rutaceae. It has a common name like sweet orange or naval orange (Azim et al., 2011) or Malta in

Bangladesh. Sweet orange trees are extensively grown in tropical and subtropical region for their appropriate growth and development. The fruit of the sweet orange can be eaten fresh or processed for its juice or fragrant peel. The fruits of sweet orange have low calories, contains no saturated body fat or cholesterol, but it contains rich dietary fiber, pectin, potassium, calcium and also contains a variety of phytochemicals and flavonoids like- hesperetin, naringin and naringenin¹(Liu, Heying, & Tanumihardjo, 2012). It is an excellent source of vitamin C (provides 53.2 mg per 100 g, about 90% of DRI) and it is rich in antioxidant activity (Azim et al., 2011; Kiong, Wan, Hussein, & Ibrahim, 2008). Malta helps to reducing the risk for cancers (Elangovan, Sekar, & Govindasamy, 1994); chronic diseases like arthritis (Sinclair, Bartholomew, & Ramsey, 1945) and coronary heart disease (Crowell, 1999). Malta contains about 170 phytonutrients and more than 60 flavonoids with anti-tumor, anti-inflammatory, blood clot inhibiting and antioxidant properties (Etebu & Nwauzoma, 2014). These fruits are consumed all over the world and also considered as one of the major economical fruit crops in the world (Kiong et al., 2008).

Citrus sinensis (L.) plants are propagated by both sexual and asexual techniques. Commercially sweet orange trees are propagated asexually by grafting a mature cultivar on an appropriate seedling rootstock to ensure the same yield, identical fruit characteristics, and resistance to diseases. The rootstocks are generally propagated sexually through seeds and most of the commercial varieties are propagated by asexual methods (Savita, Virk, & Nagpal, 2010).

However, the cultivation of *C. sinensis* is difficult because of its slow growth (Mukhtar, Khan, Fatima, Abbas, & Shahid, 2005) and susceptibility to a large number of diseases such as, *Citrus chlorosis* (Rossetti, 1977), Citrus canker (Rossetti, 1977), Ring spot (Fawcett, 1933), Sweet orange scab (Kunta et al., 2013), Citrus black spot (Koltze, 1981), and Powdery mildew (AR, 1992). To overcome these problems plant tissue culture technology has been successfully used for the commercial production of disease free plants and to conserve the germplasm of rare (Rossetti, 1977) applied as a helpful tool to reduce the time for improvement of the sweet orange through somaclonal variation. This technique helps to improve against different abiotic stresses, low yield and conserve important citrus genotypes through exploiting somaclonal variations, somatic cell hybridization (Kobayashi, Ikeda, & Uchimiya, 1985). By using micro-propagation method, there is a chance to establish a cell line of virus free sweet orange (Azim et al., 2011).

Regeneration of *Citrus sinensis* (L.) plantlets can be achieved by a wide range of explants such as stem sections (Bhansali & Arya, 1980; C. Chang, Chen, Tsai, & Chang, 2000; Chaturvedi, 1974; I. Singh, 2002), root sections (Sauton, Mouras, & Lutz, 1982; I. Singh, 2002), root meristems (S. Singh, Ray, Bhattacharyya, & Deka, 1994), shoot and shoot tips (Murashige & Skoog, 1962; Thwe et al., 2012). Micropropagation of sweet orange mainly for obtaining virus free propagative and reduce economic losses which is caused by virus and virus like diseases. Micropropagation has been the most effective tools for commercial application mostly in herbaceous plants (Honda, Liu, & Kobayashi, 2001). Micropropagation has many advantages over conventional methods of vegetative propagation and its application in Horticulture, Agriculture and Forestry is currently expanding all over the world. Micropropagation of sweet orange is the most effective way to obtain a large number of genetically identical, physiologically uniform and developmentally normal plantlet. Tissue culture technique is used for commercial production of economically important plants (Parmessur, Aljanabi, Saumtally, & Dookun-Saumtally, 2002) especially for microbe free plants (Anand & Jeyachandran, 2004).

The present study could be a suitable tools to the scientific community to develop a high frequency of direct regeneration system of sweet orange or *Citrus sinensis* (L.) using shoot tip and nodal segment explants and to compare explants responses to different hormone concentrations.

Materials and methods

Collection of explants

In the present investigation, different parts of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L.) were used as an experimental material. Mature seeds of sweet orange were used for *in vitro* propagation. The orange seeds were collected from the local market at Rajshahi, Bangladesh. For *in vitro* culture, nodal segments and shoot tips were used as explants.

Surface sterilization

Explants were removed and grown plants and washed thoroughly in running tap water for 30 min then immersed in savlon for 10 minutes and washed several times with distilled water. Explants immersed in 70% ethanol for 1 minute. The explants were blotted in sterile filter paper to remove excess water and then remove the cutting ends.

Culture media and micropropagation

The all explants (1-2 cm) were implanted on sterile medium consisting of salts and vitamins of MS medium (Murashige & Skoog, 1962) supplemented with 8g/l Agar and 30g/l sucrose, different

combination and concentration of plant growth regulators (auxin and cytokinins) for callus induction and shoot regeneration. The optimum pH was adjacent to 5.8 by using 0.1 N NaOH (Sodium hydroxide) or 0.1 N HCl (Hydrochloric acid) and autoclave at $121\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 minutes. Cultures were incubated at $25\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ under 16 hours of photoperiod with $45\mu\text{mol m}^{-2}\text{ sec}^{-1}$ irradiance provided by cool white fluorescent light (PHILIPS 40W tubes). The regenerated callus and the micro shoots were transferred into regeneration medium for callus to form adventitious bud and shoot elongation medium containing different concentrations of BAP and combination of BAP+GA₃ and BAP+NAA individually. Individual shoots, which were grown about 3-4 cm long transferred to half strength MS medium containing BAP, GA₃ and NAA for multiple shoot formation and direct proliferation of shoot from shoot tips and nodal segments and different concentrations of IAA on root induction in MS media. The rooted plantlets were transferred into plastic cups containing soil: sand: vermiculite (1:1:1). The plantlets were maintained under the same controlled environmental conditions for 3 weeks and watered once in 2 days with half strength MS basal salts, subsequently they were transferred to polythene cover and kept in greenhouse and after four weeks the plantlets transfer to the field.

Data assortment and applied math analysis

Data were collected after 28 days of culture and all the treatment of 20 test tube cultured for each concentration statistically analyzed by using Microsoft Excel and analysis of variance (ANOVA), mean, percentage and standard errors were carried out for each conditions done by Microsoft excel and SPSS software.

Results

Effects of different concentrations and combinations of BAP, GA₃ and NAA for multiple shoot formation and direct proliferation of shoot from shoot tips and nodal segments of Citrus sinensis

Nodal segment and shoot tip of *Citrus sinensis* (L.) were cultured on MS medium containing different concentrations and combinations of BAP and also BAP with GA₃, and NAA for multiple shoot formation. Different concentrations of BAP (0.5 mg/l – 3 mg/l) in combination with GA₃ (0.1mg/l – 0.3 mg/l) and NAA (0.2 mg/l – 0.3 mg/l) were used for multiple shoot formation and shoot proliferation. Among all the different concentrations and combinations, from nodal culture the highest mean number of shoot was observed at the combination of 2 mg/l BAP+0.1 mg/l NAA respectively and the highest mean number of shoots was observed 5.6 from this combination. In case of shoot tip culture the highest number of shoot was observed at the combination of 1.5 mg/l

BAP+0.2 mg/l GA₃ respectively and the highest mean number of shoots was observed 4.4 from this combination. The percentage of shoot initiation was 85% for nodal segments and 80% for nodal segments (Table 1 & Figure 1).

Effects of different concentrations of BAP

In our study, the media supplemented with BAP, the highest shoot length was found 2.50cm and 3.15cm in nodal segments and shoot tips explants respectively (Table 1 & Figure 1). The average lowest number of multiple shoots was observed in 0.5mg/l BAP. In this combination, the average number of shoot per explants were 1.7 in shoot tips and 2.1 in nodal segments respectively, the lowest average length was observed 2.0 in shoot tips and 2.0 in nodal segments respectively.

Effects of different concentrations and combination of BAP and GA₃

For the combination of BAP and GA₃ it was observed that the highest shoot length was found in the combination of 1.5 mg/l BAP+0.2 mg/l GA₃ in nodal segments (5.20cm) and shoot tips (4.90cm) explants respectively (Table 1 & Figure 1). The average lowest number of multiple shoots was observing in 0.5 mg/l BAP +0.1 mg/l GA₃. In this combination the average number of shoot per explants were 2.5 in shoot tips and 1.5 in nodal segments respectively, the lowest average length was observed 4.5cm in shoot tips and 4.7cm in nodal segments respectively.

Effects of different concentrations and combination of BAP and NAA

It was observed that the combination of BAP and NAA, the highest shoot length was found in the combination of 1 mg/l BAP+0.2 mg/l NAA in nodal segments (4.80cm) and 2 mg/l BAP+0.1 mg/l NAA in shoot tips (4.95cm) explants respectively (Table 1 & Figure 1). The average lowest number of multiple shoots was observed in 1 mg/l BAP+0.1 mg/l NAA. In this combination the average number of shoot per explants were 2.5 in nodal segments and 2.3 in shoot tips when culture at the combination of 0.5mg/l BAP+0.1 mg/l NAA respectively, the lowest average length was observed 4.35 in shoot tips and 4.18 in nodal segments respectively.

Effects of different concentrations of IAA on root induction in MS media

In our study, the media supplemented with different concentrations of IAA, the average highest length of root was observed 4.6cm at 2.0 mg/l IAA which is followed by 3.5cm at 2.5 mg/l IAA,

3.2cm at 1.5 mg/l IAA, 2.8cm at 1.0 mg/l IAA and 2.5cm at 0.5 mg/l IAA respectively. The lowest average length was observed when media supplemented with 2.5cm at 0.5 mg/l IAA concentration respectively (Table 2& Figure 1).

Hardening and transplantation of the plantlets

The plantlets of sweet orange were subsequently subcultured and finally transferred aseptically to the greenhouse after 3 weeks of inoculation covered with polythene bag, after four weeks the plantlet were transferred to the soil. The percentage of such plantlet survivability was observed 85% (Table 2 &Figure1).

Table 1: Effects of different concentrations and combinations of BAP, GA₃ and NAA for multiple shoot formation and direct proliferation of shoot from shoot tips and nodal segments

Hormonal Supplement s (mg/l) with MS	Nodal segments				Shoot tips			
	No. explants inoculated	Percentage of explants responded	Mean No. of shoots	Mean length of shoots (cm)	No. explants inoculated	Percentage of explants responded	Mean No. of shoots	Mean length of shoots (cm)
BAP								
0.5	20	42	2.1	2.20 b	20	10	1.7	2.00 d
1.00	20	58	4.0	2.10 bc	20	30	2.5	2.20 c
1.5	20	67	3.0	2.00 c	20	50	1.7	2.40 c
2.0	20	77	3.5	2.50 a	20	70	2.0	3.15 a
3.0	20	18	2.6	2.30 b	20	50	2.7	2.75 b
BAP+GA₃								
0.5+0.1	20	30	1.5	4.70 d	20	40	2.5	4.50 c
1+0.1	20	50	4.7	4.90 c	20	60	4.0	4.80 ab
1.5+0.2	20	70	3.7	5.20 a	20	80	4.4	4.90 a
2.5+0.3	20	40	3.5	5.00 b	20	50	4.0	4.60 b
BAP+NAA								
0.5+0.1	20	40	3.0	4.60 ab	20	20	2.3	4.50 c
1+0.1	20	60	2.5	4.80 a	20	30	2.6	4.35 d

2.0+0.1	20	85	5.6	4.35 b	20	70	3.4	4.95 a
2.5+0.2	20	70	5.0	4.48 ab	20	50	2.7	4.65 b
3+0.3	20	50	3.5	4.18 c	20	40	3.0	4.50 c

NB: The data with same alphabets are not significantly different according to DMRT at 5% probability.

Table 2: Effects of different concentrations of IAA on root induction in MS media

Hormonal supplements (mg/l) with MS	Number of explants	Percentage of response	Mean length of root (cm)
IAA			
0.5	20	30	2.5 e
1.0	20	43	2.8 d
1.5	20	55	3.2 c
2.0	20	70	4.6 a
2.5	20	58	3.5 b

NB: The data with same alphabets are not significantly different according to DMRT at 5% probability.

Figure 1: Micropropagation of *C. sinensis* (L.) a. Seed germination; b. Multiple shoot formation; c. Shoot proliferation; d. Root induction e. Hardening and transplantation of the plantlets

Discussion

Multiplication of regenerated shoot was the major objective of the *in vitro* plant regeneration or multiplication of plant species. The hormonal concentrations have a significant effect on multiple shoot regeneration (Chaturvedi, 1974). In this experiment different concentrations and combinations of BAP and GA₃ were used with MS basal media to study their effects on multiple shoot formation from nodal segments and shoot tips. In a significant development of suitable protocol for shoot multiplication, it was observed that nodal segment explants gave better result than shoot tip explants. When MS fortified with BAP and GA₃ it was observed that the highest shoot length was found in the combination of 1.5 mg/l BAP+0.2 mg/l GA₃ in nodal segments (5.20cm) and from shoot tips 2.0 mg/l BAP+0.1 mg/l NAA (4.95cm) explants respectively. Regeneration of Citrus has been already investigated using MS medium supplemented with BA at 3 mg/l or with BA at 1 mg/l (Raman, Gosal, & Brar, 1992) the combination of BA and NAA have been shown for shoot regeneration from calli of different *Citrus spp.*. Some studies have shown use of BA alone to be better treatment for shoot regeneration in different *Citrus spp.* (Costa, Otoni, & Moore, 2002; He, Xie, Peng, & Mu, 2006). Reported shoot regeneration at BA from 0.5 – 4 mg/l for *Citrus paradise* epicotyl explants. *In vitro* grown ash gourd explants gave adventitious shoot elongation in the combination of MS + 1 mg/l BAP + 0.5 mg/l IAA (Chan, Dewi, & Boey, 2005); MS+1.6 mg/l BAP + 0.5 mg/l NAA (Haque, Sarkar, Mahmud, Rezwana, & Sikdar, 2008). It was observed that the effects of GA₃ with BAP were better for shoot multiplication directly than the effect of BAP singly in ash gourd. On the other hand, only BAP was also found to be effective for *in vitro* shoot multiplications in *Alpinia purpurata* by (B. W. CHANG & Criley, 1993) and *Cucumis melo* by (Huda & Sikdar, 2006). Some other plant species required more than one type of cytokinin for shoot proliferation such as *Techtona grandis* (Davanagere, Sherif, & Goswami, 1999) MS fortified with combination of BAP, IBA GA₃ was very good for shoot initiation and elongation from apical meristem of *Citrus sinensis* (Kobayashi et al., 1985). It was observed by (Haque et al., 2008) the ability to produce 3.1 shoots per explant with a response of 54% in *C. sinensis* on BA+GA₃ (1.8+0.7 µM) supplemented MS medium. Best responses for multiple shoot regeneration were obtained by (Debnath, Roy, Ahmed, & Hossain, 2000) from the nodal segments of *B. hispidaon* MS + 1.5 mg/l BAP and they observed the frequency of multiple shoot regeneration from nodal segments was 90%. The frequency of multiple shoots regeneration in *Tricosanthes dioica* were 92% and 100% for shoot tips and nodal segments respectively when

cultured on the medium MS + 2 mg/l BAP + 0.1 mg/l NAA (Kathal, Bhatnagar, & Bhojwani, 1988). The fortifications of cytokinin for multiple shoot induction at lower concentration have been reported by (Anand & Jeyachandran, 2004; M. Singh, Mishra, & Bhatnagar, 1996). In *Zehneria scabra* (L.F) for shoot multiplication, high concentration of BAP and IAA was used by (Chakravarty & Goswami, 1999). Maximum shoots per nodal explants on MS medium containing 1.0 mg/l and 2.0 mg/l BAP + 0.2 mg/l NAA was found to be the best medium for the production of multiple shoots in water melon (M. Singh et al., 1996). (Kobayashi et al., 1985) Found that combination of 1.5mg/lBAP+0.1 mg/l NAA was more suitable for adventitious multiple shoot formation in trestle ground (*Citrullus vulgaris*).

In our present study, the media supplemented with different concentration of IAA, the average highest length of root was observed 4.6cm at 2.0 mg/l IAA. On the contrary, NAA was found to give better response in *Citrus acida* (Peña et al., 1995). Other reports which showed NAA to be better rooting hormone for *Citrus spp.*(Kathal et al., 1988; Peña et al., 1995; Rani et al., 2004; USMAN, SANA, & Fatima, 2005). Root induction is obligatory for successful plant regeneration. Efficient rooting was achieved on V₂ strength MS medium supplemented with 1 mg/l IBA and 100% micro-shoots produced root. (Sauton et al., 1982) Achieved good result for root induction using only IBA in *C. melo*. MS medium supplemented with 0.6 mg/l NAA, gave 70% response. But when 0.8 mg/l NAA was used 40% was the highest response. (Kathal et al., 1988) were achieved efficient rooting using half strength of MS + 0.5 mg/l NAA in *Trichosanthes dioica* (Ajayi, Berjak, Kioko, Dulloo, & Vodouhe, 2006; Kathal et al., 1988) with MS media on watermelon. Shoot elongation was simultaneously observed along with root induction using NAA in *Zehneria scabra* (L.F.) (Chaturvedi, 1974). (Ahmad & Anis, 2005) Achieved best normal root growth on full strength MS medium supplemented with 0.1 mg/l NAA and 0.2 mg/l KIN in *Telfair occidentalis*.

References

- Ahmad, N., & Anis, M. (2005). In vitro mass propagation of *Cucumis sativus* L. from nodal segments. *Turkish journal of botany*, 29(3), 237-240.
- Ajayi, S. A., Berjak, P., Kioko, J. I., Dulloo, M. E., & Vodouhe, R. S. (2006). Observations on in vitro behaviour of the zygotic axes of fluted pumpkin. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 5(15).

- Anand, S., & Jeyachandran, R. (2004). In vitro multiple shoot regeneration from nodal explants of *Zehneria scabra* (Lf) Sonder-An important medicinal climber. *Plant tissue cult*, 14(2), 101-106.
- AR, S. H. (1992). *Preliminary epidemiological study of powdery mildew (Oidium tingitaninum) on Citrus sinensis*. Paper presented at the Asian citrus rehabilitation conference. Malang (Indonesia). 1989.
- Azim, F., Rahman, M., Prodhan, S. H., Sikdar, S. U., Zobayer, N., & Ashrafuzzaman, M. (2011). Development of efficient callus initiation of Malta (*Citrus sinensis*) through tissue culture. *International Journal of Agricultural Research, Innovation and Technology*, 1(1-2), 64-68.
- Bhansali, R. R., & Arya, H. (1980). Organogenesis in *Citrus limettioides* (Sweet lime) callus culture. *Phytomorphology*.
- Chakravarty, B., & Goswami, B. (1999). Plantlet regeneration from long-term callus cultures of *Citrus acida* Roxb. and the uniformity of regenerated plants. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 82(1-2), 159-169.
- Chan, L. K., Dewi, P. R., & Boey, R. (2005). Effect of plant growth regulators on regeneration of plantlets from bud cultures of *Cymbopogon nardus* L. and the detection of essential oils from their vitro plantlets. *Journal of Plant Biology*, 48(1), 142-146.
- CHANG, B. W., & Criley, R. A. (1993). Clonal propagation of pink ginger in vitro. *HortScience*, 28(12).
- Chang, C., Chen, C.-T., Tsai, Y.-C., & Chang, W.-C. (2000). A tissue culture protocol for propagation of a rare plant, *Lilium speciosum* Thunb. var. *gloriosoides* Baker. *Botanical Bulletin of Academia Sinica*, 41.
- Chaturvedi, H. (1974). Clonal propagation of *Citrus* from somatic callus cultures. *Hort Science*, 9, 118-120.
- Costa, M., Otoni, W., & Moore, G. (2002). An evaluation of factors affecting the efficiency of *Agrobacterium*-mediated transformation of *Citrus paradisi* (Macf.) and production of transgenic plants containing carotenoid biosynthetic genes. *Plant Cell Reports*, 21(4), 365-373.
- Crowell, P. L. (1999). Prevention and therapy of cancer by dietary monoterpenes. *The Journal of nutrition*, 129(3), 775S-778S.

- Davanagere, B., Sherif, S., & Goswami, D. (1999). A feasibility study of a solar desiccant air-conditioning system—Part I: psychrometrics and analysis of the conditioned zone. *International journal of energy research*, 23(1), 7-21.
- Debnath, R., Roy, S., Ahmed, G., & Hossain, M. (2000). Micropropagation of patal (*Trichosanthes dioica* Roxb.) from nodal segment and shoot tip. *Plant tissue cult*, 10(2), 125-130.
- Elangovan, V., Sekar, N., & Govindasamy, S. (1994). Chemopreventive potential of dietary bioflavonoids against 20-methylcholanthrene-induced tumorigenesis. *Cancer letters*, 87(1), 107-113.
- Etebu, E., & Nwauzoma, A. (2014). A review on sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L Osbeck): health, diseases and management. *American Journal of Research Communication*, 2(2), 33-70.
- Fawcett, H. (1933). New symptoms of psorosis, indicating a virus disease of citrus. *Phytopathology*, 23, 930.
- Haque, M., Sarkar, M., Mahmud, M., Rezwana, D., & Sikdar, B. (2008). In vitro propagation of pumpkin and ash gourd through nodal segments. *Journal of Bio-Science*, 16, 67-71.
- He, X., Xie, D., Peng, Q., & Mu, L. (2006). *Plant regeneration from cotyledon of chieh-qua (Benincasa hispida Cogn. var. chieh-qua How)*. Paper presented at the XXVII International Horticultural Congress-IHC2006: International Symposium on Plant Biotechnology: From Bench to 764.
- Honda, H., Liu, C., & Kobayashi, T. (2001). Large-scale plant micropropagation *Plant Cells* (pp. 157-182): Springer.
- Huda, A., & Sikdar, B. (2006). In vitro plant production through apical meristem culture of bitter gourd (*Momordica charantia* L.). *Plant Tissue Culture and Biotechnology*, 16(1), 31-36.
- Kathal, R., Bhatnagar, S., & Bhojwani, S. S. (1988). Regeneration of plants from leaf explants of *Cucumis melo* cv. Pusa Sharbati. *Plant Cell Reports*, 7(6), 449-451.
- Kiong, A. L. P., Wan, L. S., Hussein, S., & Ibrahim, R. (2008). Induction of somatic embryos from different explants of *Citrus sinensis*. *Journal of Plant Sciences*, 3(1), 18-32.
- Kobayashi, S., Ikeda, I., & Uchimiya, H. (1985). Conditions for high frequency embryogenesis from orange (*Citrus sinensis* Osb.) protoplasts. *Plant cell, tissue and organ culture*, 4(3), 249-259.
- Koltze, J. (1981). Epidemiology and control of citrus black spot in South Africa. *Plant Disease*, 65(12), 945-950.

- Kunta, M., Rascoe, J., Sa, P. B. d., Timmer, L. W., Palm, M. E., Graça, J. V. d., . . . Satpute, A. (2013). Sweet orange scab with a new scab disease" syndrome" of citrus in the USA associated with *Elsinoë australis*. *Tropical Plant Pathology*, 38(3), 203-212.
- Liu, Y., Heying, E., & Tanumihardjo, S. A. (2012). History, global distribution, and nutritional importance of citrus fruits. *Comprehensive reviews in Food Science and Food safety*, 11(6), 530-545.
- Mukhtar, R., Khan, M. M., Fatima, B., Abbas, M., & Shahid, A. (2005). In vitro regeneration and multiple shoots induction in *Citrus reticulata* (Blanco). *Int. J. Agri. Biol*, 7(3), 414-416.
- Murashige, T., & Skoog, F. (1962). A revised medium for rapid growth and bio assays with tobacco tissue cultures. *Physiologia plantarum*, 15(3), 473-497.
- Parmessur, Y., Aljanabi, S., Saumtally, S., & Dookun-Saumtally, A. (2002). Sugarcane yellow leaf virus and sugarcane yellows phytoplasma: elimination by tissue culture. *Plant pathology*, 51(5), 561-566.
- Peña, L., Cervera, M., Juárez, J., Navarro, A., Pina, J. A., Durán-Vila, N., & Navarro, L. (1995). Agrobacterium-mediated transformation of sweet orange and regeneration of transgenic plants. *Plant Cell Reports*, 14(10), 616-619.
- Raman, H., Gosal, S., & Brar, D. (1992). Plant regeneration from callus cultures of *Citrus limon* and *C. jambhiri*. *Crop improvement*, 19(2), 100-103.
- Rani, G., Singh, B., Sharma, S., Rehan, L., Zaidi, A., Nagpal, A., & Virk, G. (2004). Micropropagation of Kinnow (*Citrus nobilis* x *Citrus deliciosa*) through nodal segments. *J Ind Bot Soc*, 83, 26-29.
- Rossetti, V. (1977). *Citrus canker in Latin America: A review*. Paper presented at the Proceedings of the International Society of Citriculture.
- Sauton, A., Mouras, A., & Lutz, A. (1982). Plant regeneration from citrus root meristems. *Journal of Horticultural Science*, 57(2), 227-231.
- Savita, V., Virk, G., & Nagpal, A. (2010). Effect of explant type and different plant growth regulators on callus induction and plantlet regeneration in *Citrus jambhiri* Lush. *Environ. We Int. J. Sci. Tech*, 5, 97-106.
- Sinclair, W. B., Bartholomew, E., & Ramsey, R. (1945). Analysis of the organic acids of orange juice. *Plant Physiology*, 20(1), 3.
- Singh, I. (2002). Micropropagation in citrus—A review. *Agricultural Reviews*, 23(1), 1-13.

- Singh, M., Mishra, A., & Bhatnagar, S. (1996). In vitro production of plants from cotyledon explants of *Cucumis melo* L. and their successful transfer to field. *Phytomorphology*, 46, 395-402.
- Singh, S., Ray, B., Bhattacharyya, S., & Deka, P. (1994). In vitro propagation of *Citrus reticulata* Blanco and *Citrus limon* Burm. f. *HortScience*, 29(3), 214-216.
- Thwe, A. A., Mai, N. T. T., Li, X., Kim, Y., Kim, Y. B., Uddin, M. R., . . . Lee, M. Y. (2012). Production of astragaloside and flavones from adventitious root cultures of *Astragalus membranaceus* var. *mongholicus*. *Plant Omics*, 5(5), 466.
- USMAN, M., SANA, M., & Fatima, B. (2005). In vitro multiple shoot induction from nodal explants of *Citrus* cultivars. *Journal of Central European Agriculture*, 6(4), 435-442.

Authors name and details

Md. Tauhidul Islam

Md. Tauhidul Islam completed his MS degree from the Department of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. He started his project work on Plant Tissue Culture from the very beginning of his research for the last 2 years.

Sumon Karmakar

Sumon Karmakar completed his Bachelor degree from the Department of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. Currently he is studying as an MS thesis student in the field of Plasma Agriculture. He started his project work on Plant Tissue Culture for the last 3 years. He has experience in Plant tissue culture, Bioinformatics, Biostatistics, Molecular biology, Plasma agriculture, Field trials and Irrigation system of Strawberry, Maize, Wheat and Potato plants.

Mutasim Billah

Mutasim Billah is currently working at the University of Rajshahi as an MS student in the field of Microbiology. He started his project work with Plasma Agricultural Science as well as Plant Tissue Culture for the last 3 years. He is also experienced in Bioinformatics, Biostatistics, Molecular biology field trial of maize and wheat cultivation system.

Md. Nazmus Sakib

Md. Nazmus Sakib completed his Bachelor degree from the Department of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh and is currently working as an MS student in the field of Microbiology. He has been working on Microbiology as well as Plant Tissue Culture for the last 2 years.

Md. Faruk Hasan

Md. Faruk Hasan completed his MS and M.Phil degree from the Department of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. He took training on Biotechnology from Japan and currently working as an Associate Professor. He has expertise on Plant Tissue Culture and biotechnology.

Dr. Md. Asadul Islam

Md. Asadul Islam completed his MS and M.Phil degree from the University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. He completed PhD course from China and currently working as a Professor in the Department of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. He has expertise on Plant Tissue Culture, Rice research and biotechnology.

Dr. Biswanath Sikdar

Biswanath Sikdar completed his MS degree from the University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. He completed M.Phil and PhD course from India and currently working as a Professor and lab head in the Department of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. He has expertise on Genetic Engineering, Plant Tissue Culture, and Biotechnology.

Dr. Uzzal Kumar Acharjee

Uzzal Kumar Acharjee completed his MS and PGD-in-IT degree from the University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. He completed PhD course from Japan and currently working as an Associate Professor in the Department of Genetic Engineering and Biotechnology, University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh. He has expertise on Developmental Biology, Plant and Animal Tissue Culture, Axon Guidance and Molecular Biology.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the Ministry of Science and Technology (MoST), Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh for financial support to carry the whole work (No.3900.0000.09.06.217/2BS 91/170).

Conflicts of Interest

None of the authors has any financial or personal relationships that could inappropriately influence or bias the content of the paper.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Assets of publishing with NAAR

- Global archiving of articles
- Immediate, free online access for all
- Rigorous peer review process
- Authors retain copyrights
- DOI for all articles

<https://twasp.info/journal/home>

Submit your article : editor@twasp.info